

PACIFICUS

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“A Mother’s Lie”

She whispered soft, “It’s just a scratch,”
As tears welled in my eyes.
Her gentle hands, a warm embrace,
Concealed the truth in sighs.

She promised, “Monsters aren’t real, my love,”
Yet shadows filled the night.
Her lullabies, a shield so strong,
Kept darkness out of sight.

She swore, “I’m fine, don’t worry, dear,”
Though tired lines betrayed.
Her aching hands still held me close,
As years began to fade.

A mother’s lie is sweet and kind,
To ease a child’s pain,
A love so pure, it hides the truth,
Again, and yet again.

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